

St. Kitts & Nevis / Los Angeles / info@beyondcapitalmarkets.com

Beyond Capital Markets is the first global community supporting financial and impact innovation. Our integrated venture development platform, powered by blockchain, provides acceleration, fundraising, and growth development to over 1,000 early stage companies, financial institutions, governments and corporates.

Crypto-Impact Investing : Financing the Next Generation Economy

“You can’t connect the dots looking forward; you can only connect them looking backwards.” — Steve Jobs

THE OPPORTUNITY

Wealth creation is the fundamental driver of individual and social well being. Initial coin offerings (ICOs) crowdsales & investments have surpassed Venture Capital (VC) raising over \$4B in 2017. This represents an almost 40 fold from \$96.3M in 2016.

While the market is saturated with blockchain infrastructure development, payments and speculative trading, we see a move towards blockchain use cases for and by businesses.

More than a fad, data as a digital asset is now the “**new oil**”, fuelling new emergent business models while transforming old traditional in-efficient market sectors to high growth efficient industries through the radical transparency of crypto assets (currencies) and decentralised ledger technologies (blockchain). These real world applications can totally transform ecosystems through wealth creation.

With the many challenges of access to finance for financing early stage ventures and industries, crypto impact investing can help accelerate wealth goals by creating a powerful alternative financing method for supporting projects with the ability to fix negative socio-economic problems with entrepreneurship and investing. Fixing the world and earning a return on investment can spur positive impacts economically, socially and environmentally with an in-built profit incentive which fuels market growth.

THE BOOTCAMP

In this interactive bootcamp is a one-day workshop where you'll learn the fundamentals of a strong crypto impact investing plan and how to align dreamy market trends with realistic broad based economic and financial goals.

It was created for those interested in gaining a deeper understanding and getting a holistic perspective of cryptocurrencies and all the available impact investment options (i.e. trading, funds, trusts), technology background and security considerations. This is vital information you can start using immediately.

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Looking for financing for a new venture? If you don't know where to start or don't even know what it really is then this interactive bootcamp is the perfect first step.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

You may not be able to make it rain and be the next Warren Buffet but we can teach you how to not get scammed and create a realistic crypto impact investing wealth plan while contributing to next generation economic development.

Through hands-on practical applications, this bootcamp includes five (5) sessions:

Part 1 - Rise of Digital Assets and Crypto Assets as a New Asset Class

Understanding the shift from physical to the digital revolution

Intangible secure property rights

Friction in Trade & lower transaction costs and economic growth

Network size and growth

Democratisation of Finance

Part 2 - Understanding Blockchain: How Cryptocurrencies Really Works

Introduction to Decentralised Governance & Blockchain Technologies

Understanding types of Cryptocurrencies and their similarities/differences

Cryptoeconomics and the long tail

Part 3 - Understanding Cryptocurrency Markets vs. Financial Markets

Market similarities and differences; pros and cons

Learn what makes cryptocurrency increase/decrease in price

How to conduct research: Understanding historical performances and forecasts

How to buy online: Differences in brokerages and exchanges

Navigating the regulatory landscape & tax implications

Cryptocurrency buying & selling tools (i.e. wallets, storages, browsers)

Part 4 - Cryptocurrency Investment Strategies: Short vs Long Term

Debunking investing trends - the good, the scams, & underperformers

Short term investing - pros & cons

Long term investing - pros & cons

Active vs passive cryptocurrency investment options

Part 5 - Integrating Cryptocurrencies in Retirement Portfolios

Managing market and personal expectations

Diversification considerations

Risk management - How to protect your investments

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WHAT YOU WILL NOT LEARN

Cryptocurrency day trading or mining
How to start a Cryptocurrency hedge fund
How to fundraise via ICO

WHO SHOULD ATTEND?

The session has been designed for both institutional and individual

Financial Managers
Management Consultants
SME & Business Coaches
Policy Makers
NGOs
Wealth Managers
Corporate Service Providers
Independent Investors
Stock market investors
Retirement portfolio investors
New cryptocurrency investors (not traders)

PERKS:

- Curated list of Cryptocurrency resources: Recommended blogs, books, experts to follow, companies of note, local organizations and recommended conferences
- 30 min advisory session
- 5 BCAP Tokens (Pre-ICO)

BOOTCAMP FACILITATION

SMES/STARTUPS - US\$50
INDEPENDENT INVESTORS/CONSULTANTS - US\$100
INSTITUTIONS -US \$200

OPTIONAL ADVISORY PACKAGES:

Cryptofinance Investment Facilitation Advisory (Asset Protection and Structuring) - US\$1000
Crypto Impact Investment Portfolio Construction /Personal Finance Advisory Session - US\$1000

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Team Leadership/ Facilitators

TELLY V. ONU

Managing Director , Beyond Capital Markets / Lead Project Manager & Architect

Ms. Telly Valerie Onu has been at the forefront of the financial innovation ecosystem with over 17 years' experience as a financial and impact innovator, digital economist and transformation expert and thought leader. She has designed, and led multimillion dollar projects and implementation teams. Launched and led a global strategy and management consulting firm since 2000, and has since secured strategic partnerships with the World Bank Group, the Eastern Caribbean Central Bank, Microsoft, Technical Centre for Rural and Agriculture Cooperation (CTA), Savings Banks Foundation for International Cooperation (SBFIC) (Sparkassenstiftung für internationale Kooperation) to name a few. She is passionate about Innovation and Transformation which led to the establishment of Innovatethenext Foundation in 2014 an innovation ecosystem catalyst supporting industry and sector transformation. Telly is the acting director of the St. Kitts and Nevis Coalition of Service Industries and is responsible for enabling the growth of the services industry inclusive of the creative services sector.

Ms. Onu holds an Executive Masters in e-Governance, specialising in complex project design implementation & management, cryptography, public key infrastructures (PKI), decentralised networked governance, innovation and transformation from the Swiss University of Technology (EPFL) (Network Industry Economics). She also holds a Postgraduate Certificate (PgCert) in Digital Currency from the University of Nicosia in Cyprus, PgCert Internet Governance from DiploFoundation in Switzerland & Malta, PgCert in International Trade Policy & Law and is a Certified Ecommerce Consultant with the focus on e-finance from the Institute of Certified E-Commerce Consultants (ICECC), USA, Ms. Onu is currently a fellow at the Frankfurt School of Management and Finance in Germany, specializing in Climate Adaptation Finance and Crypto Financing. She holds numerous vendor certification including but not limited to Visa electronic payments.

Recent Blockchain & Project Enterprise Architecture & Management Experience (2014 - Present):

- Design and Delivery of Blockchain & ICO curriculum and Advisory to 17 impact startups on blockchain architecture , design and ICO crowdsale preparation on Ethereum, IOTA and Stellar blockchains - ICO Crowdsale for Impact Accelerator (November, 2017 - Present)
- Delivered presentations on The AgTech Landscape & the Readiness for Financing of Startups in Africa & Use of Blockchain, Caribbean and Pacific CTA ICT4AgOutlook, Rhenen, Netherlands (September, 2017)
- Climate Mitigation and Adaptation Opportunities using Blockchain - Hack4Climate Hackathon, Paramaribo, Suriname (August 2017)
- Insuretech & Blockchain – Opportunities for Climate Change Finance Adaptation” – Frankfurt, Germany (June 2017)
- Chapter author for upcoming Fintech Circle's The Insuretech Book, Internationalizing Insuretech & Blockchain Applications, May 2017 to present (published January 2018)
- Next generation funding models for emerging market startups and SMEs – Digital Finance Services Workshop – ITU -Trinidad & Tobago – (April 2017)

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- Member, Working Group on the Eastern Caribbean Currency Union (ECCU) Payment System and Financial Innovation - (Since 2016)
- Decrypting Crypto-Currencies & The Role Of The Central Bank – Eastern Caribbean Central Bank (ECCB) Workshop – St. Kitts and Nevis (December, 2016)
- Presentation on Innovation Impact and Impact Investment for Startups - Pitch Agrihack 2016 – Nairobi, Kenya (November, 2016)
- Presentation on Digital currency and the Financial System for Financial Practitioners in the Eastern Caribbean Currency Union (ECCU)– Eastern Caribbean Central Bank (ECCB) Workshop St. Kitts and Nevis (October 2016)
- Designed a Regional Custom Relationship Management (CRM) System for the Coalition of Service Industries (October 2015 - January 2017)
- Designed IT Integration Programme to assist with post-merger of two banking institutions for the Eastern Caribbean Financial Holdings (ECFH) Company Limited in June 2016.
- Leads the Ministry of Education’s Microsoft Digital Transformation Program - (2015 to Present) responsible for selecting and onboarding a cloud-based User Identity Management solution for use with cloud-based partner platforms as well as Technology upgrades.
- Established and managed a \$10M -Small Enterprise Assistance Fund (SEAF) and onlending programme. Also evaluated long-term technology solutions and vendors as part of \$1M discretionary budget to address business needs (e.g.Loan Management; Configure/Price/Quote solutions) and technical needs (such as Enterprise Service Bus) & designed high-level solutions and partner integration for multi-system, enterprise efforts, including Microsoft Dynamics. (2014-2015)
- Mapped the Financial Enterprise Architecture for all the Eastern Caribbean Indigenous Banks and designed a IT consolidation framework, strategy and implementation plan. (June -October 2012)
- Drafted and consulted on the electronic transactions bill for St (Christopher) Kitts and Nevis - Bill was passed into law in 2011. - (2010-2011)

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MCKENZIE M. SLAUGHTER

Founding Partner, Beyond Capital Markets / Lead Product Developer & User Experience Designer

McKenzie M. Slaughter is a finance and technology entrepreneur and investor with a background in payments, lending, wealth management, alternative investments. McKenzie is CEO and General Partner at Prohaus Group, an alternative impact investment holdings company focused on impact innovation with fintech and blockchain at the core foundation. Holdings include Prohaus Lab, Capital, and Ratings.

McKenzie got her start in venture capital building startup ecosystems as former COO and advisor to the CEO at MD Idea Lab, a Boston-based accelerator for digital healthcare startups. For the past few years her focus has been fintech and impact innovation ecosystem development across Africa, Caribbean and Latin America in partnership with The World Bank, InfoDev, and CTA. She is an active mentor and capital partner with several venture programs focused on the development of entrepreneurs in Latin America, the Caribbean and Africa. Most recent venture programs McKenzie has worked with are World Bank's PitchIT Caribbean, Pitch Agrihack (CTA), InnovatetheNext Foundation, Stanford Latino Entrepreneurship Initiative, and Parallel 18.

Introduced to computer science at 16, by age 18 started programming at NASA Langley McKenzie received a Bachelors of Science in Mathematics and Computer Science from Hampton University, and an M.B.A. in Finance from Hofstra University. McKenzie is a has also recipient of CAIA / 100 Women in Hedge Funds scholar and Women in Fintech Powerlist 2017.

Recent Blockchain & Product Management Experience (2016 - Present):

- Investor & ICO Readiness Training for AgTech, Africa Green Revolution Forum and Pitch Agrihack West, September 2017 (Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire)
- Acquisition due diligence for Bitcoin peer to peer lending platform, December 2016 - September 2017
- Cryptoinvesting professional certification program development for women, November 2016
- ICO toolbox creator for fintech and impact ventures, November 2017
- Lead developer for stock and cryptocurrency trading platform for women, 2016 to present
- Advisor, currency robo advisory platform Freeman Capital, July 2017 to present
- Cryptoinvesting Bootcamp instructor, November 2017 to present
- Chapter author for upcoming Fintech Circle's The Insuretech Book, Internationalizing Insuretech & Blockchain Applications, May 2017 to present (published January 2018)
- ICO Advisor to 17 blockchain startups, November 2017 to present
- Lead coder for ICO smart contracts for 20+ blockchain projects, September 2017 to present
- Lead designer for financial wellness and crypto hardware jewelry for female cryptoinvestors, October 2017
- Design and Delivery of Blockchain/ ICO curriculum and Advisory to 17 impact startups on ICO structuring & preparation - ICO Crowdsale for Impact Accelerator (Nov, 2017 - Present)
- Lead developer for cryptocurrency funding platforms for Beyond Capital Markets and several fintech projects, 2015 to Present

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Full Stack & Advisory Services Overview

Pre-ICO & ICO Services

Blockchain Enterprise Architecture & ICO Project Design and Development

Blockchain and related technologies such as distributed ledgers (DLT), consensus algorithms, cryptography/ hashing strategies, and smart contracts have the potential to change the way many organizations share data and execute business processes across a network of companies. In many business and industry, this requires a strategic adoption of the blockchain into the Enterprise Architecture. We will work with clients on their core ideas, and support the development of a robust business model , token model's utility and purpose, tokenomics and structuring to ensure that the ICO Crowdsale rollout is not only successful but sustainable. We work with clients to ensure that all the socio-economic and technical details of the concepts are deliverable on the blockchain along with the required visual brand presence and investor documentation.

ICO Regulatory & International Legal Resources

Our legal resources are highly experienced in intellectual property, blockchain, ecommerce, crypto laws and ICOs and well versed in conducting cross jurisdictional regulatory and legal reviews providing legal options and recommendations on the token concepts, and documentation. They also provide Support in legal drafting as needed.

ICO Crowdsale Technology Development & Project Management

We create secure smart contracts (Tokens that a fit for purpose along with hosting of the crowdsale, management and deployment during ICO, risk management assessment and measures for smart contract wallets for the ICO. We also project manage any technology development to help the client set up all the the necessary technology tools required to support an ICO.

Performance Marketing for ICO Promotion

We offer performance management solutions which include marketing go-to market strategies comprising of several approaches and tactical planning inclusive of product placement strategies, strategic locations, events and themes, identification and deployment of marketing automation tools , Bounty Campaign structuring and multilingual approaches, identification of key influencers, and campaign project management and impact measurements

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Post ICO Services

Full Stack Product & Project Management for Blockchain & Fintech Solutions

Our blockchain as a service solution accelerates the development of customized web and app platforms that can be utilized for blockchain and cryptocurrency based projects across Banking, Agriculture, Healthcare, Data Science, Clean Energy, etc. Utilizing of our private blockchain technology network, we're able to integrate a full suite of APIs and software, test and launch without the cost or risk of deploying it in-house. As interim Full Stack Product and Project Managers, we ensure your project is delivered on time and within budget by managing both the technical and operational requirements. Expertise in blockchain include Ethereum, IOTA, Stellar, and Ripple and their relevant coding languages.

KEY CAPABILITIES

Full Service Proof of Concept Development:
Idea Generation & Project Discovery Sessions
Blockchain / Smart Contract & Multichain Architecture
API & Software Sourcing & Integration
Front End Development & Design
User Experience Design & Testing

SPECIALTIES

Cryptocurrency Wallet Web & App Platforms
Cryptocurrency Ecommerce & Marketplaces
Cryptocurrency Exchange & Trading Platforms
Cryptocurrency Regulatory Framework Development
ICO Funding Platforms
ICO Jurisdictional Regulatory Review
Offshore Incorporation Services
Decentralised Organisational Structuring
Smart Contract Code Development
Product Supply Chain Development

NOTABLE TECHNOLOGY PARTNERS

Microsoft, Blockchain Division (London)
Espeo Software
IBM Blockchain Platform
Visa Foundation (Policy)
Optimus

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CURRENT CLIENTS & PARTNERS

Eastern Caribbean Central Bank (ECCB) - St. Kitts & Nevis

Beyond Capital Markets ICO for Impact Accelerator portfolio companies (17):

Earth Loans, Agroplexi, Circular Feed, Farmsai, Farmovo, Freeman Capital, Amarin Financial Group (Africa, Caribbean, & Latin America, US)

Prohaus Lab portfolio companies (5):

Tulla Health, Beauty & The Bull, Osusu Labs, Procurable (US & Caribbean)

Contact Information

To schedule a meeting or discovery session, please contact Telly V. Onu

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